

MERGERS IN INDIAN BANKING SECTOR: PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF PRE AND POST MERGERS WITH REFERENCE TO INDIAN OVERSEAS BANK AND KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK

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Abstract

Banking industry is one among the rapidly growing industry in India. The growth rate in this sector has been remarkable. Mergers have paved way to a new dimension to our banking industries. The intense competition and challenge from multinational players have urged both the public and private sector banks to gain a competitive advantage through mergers and acquisitions. This paper looks into the various mergers and acquisitions taken place in Indian banking sectors and its long-term implications. The paper deals with the types of mergers, legal framework, approval of Reserve bank of India and also makes a comparison of the pre and post-merger performance of Indian overseas bank and Kotak Mahindra bank with the help of various financial performance parameters such as profitability, liquidity, number of branches, number of employees etc. The emergence of online banking and e-commerce have significant influence in this sector leading to heavy competition. In this context this study assumes to be important.

Key words: Banking sector, Mergers and Acquisitions, public and private sector, Indian overseas bank, Kotak Mahindra

INTRODUCTION

The banking sector plays an important role in every economy and is one of the fastest growing sectors in India. Domestic banks and public and private companies are increasingly looking at achieving competitive advantage by selecting mergers and acquisitions, regardless of the fierce competition and challenge from multinational players. As a result, mergers and acquisitions are in order today. Indian commercial banks are witnessing major changes in the regulatory environment, the growth of off-balance sheet risk management financial instruments, the introduction of e-commerce and online banking and the integration of the financial industry. All these forces have made the Indian banking industry extremely competitive. Mergers and acquisitions in banks are very common worldwide. These trends were seen in the early 50's in countries like the USA, the United Kingdom, Japan and European countries.

II. MERGERS IN INDIA

The mergers in India have increased in various sectors, especially after the new economic policy of 1991 that opened the way for global markets. In 1968, the Indian government witnessed the ordinance and the nationalization of the 14 largest commercial banks in the country. These fourteen banks comprise 80% of the total bank deposits in our country. The 1980s witnessed another wave of nationalization, with six commercial banks coming under government control. With this big leap, ninety-one percent of the banking sector is under the direct control of the

Government of India. With this, the number of nationalized banks in India has increased to twenty. Shortly thereafter, in 1993, the government made another breakthrough in economic growth and merged with the banks. New Bank of India merged with Punjab National Bank (PNB) This is the first merger between nationalized banks, witnessed so far in Indian history, and consequently, the number of nationalized banks in India has declined from twenty to nineteen, and continues to be so. The banking sector in India has witnessed many mergers. Factors such as the restructuring of weak banks; Economies of scale; Market expansion; Business consolidation etc.

Looking at the history of the merger of the banking sector in India, they were initially aimed at protecting the interests of the weak banks' customers, but few mergers have taken place in the post-liberalization period. Different reasons. The Indian economy, one of the world's fastest growing economies, is poised to maintain its position despite the global financial crisis and recession. India has been able to overcome the global financial crisis due to better control, prudent financial oversight and proactive policies. India's growth is mainly driven by domestic consumption and investment. There was no direct exposure to Indian sub-prime mortgage assets or failed institutions of the Indian banking system. There have been two mergers in the Indian banking sector during this period, one on consolidation between the profitable public sector banks. The other was between two private sector banks that had profits for the merger of the merger. In this case, the study of the performance of voluntarily merged banks is of importance

Table no.1
Mergers in India

Acquiring bank	Targeted bank	Year of merger
Kotak Mahindra	ING vayasa bank	2014
ICICI bank	Bank of Rajasthan	2010
HDFC bank	Centurion bank of Punjab	2008
Indian overseas bank	Bharat overseas bank	2007
Federal bank	Ganesh bank of Kurandwad	2006
Industrial development bank of India	United western bank	
Centurion bank of Punjab	Lord Krishna bank	
ICICI bank	Sangli bank	
Bank of Punjab	Centurion bank	2005
Industrial development bank of India	IDBI abank ltd	2004
Bank of Baroda	South Gujarat local area bank	
Oriental bank of commerce	Global trust bank	
Punjab national bank	Nedungadi bankLtd	2003
ICICI bank	ICICI Ltd	2002
Bank of Baroda	Banaras state bank	
ICICI bank Ltd	Bank of Madura	2001
HDFC bank Ltd	Times bank Ltd	2000
Bank of Baroda	Bareilly Co-op Ltd	1999
Union bank of India	Sikkim bank Ltd	
Oriental bank of commerce	Bari Doab bank Ltd	1997

Oriental bank of commerce	Punjab Co-op Ltd	1996
State bank of India	Kashinath state bank	1995
Bank of India	Bank of karad Ltd	1994
Punjab national bank	New bank of India	1993

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have been conducted to examine the impact of mergers and Acquisition.

Anand Manoj & Singh Jagandeep (2008) studied the impact of merger announcements of five banks in the Indian Banking Sector on the shareholder bank. These mergers were the Times Bank merged with the HDFC Bank, the Bank of Madurai with the ICICI Bank, the ICICI Ltd with the ICICI Bank, the Global Trust Bank merged with the Oriental Bank of commerce and the Bank of Punjab merged with the centurion Bank. The announcement of merger of Bank had positive impact on shareholder's wealth.

Sinha Pankaj & Gupta Sushant (2011), studied a pre and post analysis of firms and concluded that it had positive effect on profitability, in most of the cases deteriorated liquidity. After the period of few years of Merger and Acquisitions(M&As) it came to the point that companies may have been able to leverage the synergies arising out of the merger and Acquisition that have not been able to manage their liquidity. Study showed the comparison of pre and post analysis of the firms. It also indicated the positive effects on the basis of some financial parameter like Earnings before Interest and Tax (EBIT), Return on shareholder funds, Profit margin, Interest Coverage, Current Ratio and Cost Efficiency etc.

Prashantha athma and A. Bhavani (2016), studied an analysis of pre and post-merger performance of SBI and HDFC bank and concluded that During the post-merger period, all the key parameters displayed an increasing trend excepting Number of Employees and Profits in case of SBI and Number of Employees in case of HDFC Bank. Overall growth is observed in the performance of both the banks in key parameters, and productivity ratios, and the same is ascertained by employing the statistical tools.

Objectives

1. To analyse the purpose and benefits of mergers
2. To analyse the performance of key parameters of select banks

Methodology

Sources of Data: The study is based on Secondary Sources which includes the Annual Reports of the Select Banks; RBI Database- Profile of Banks –various issues; research publications etc.

Period of Study: The Period of the Study is the Post Liberalisation Period i.e., from 1991 to 31st March 2019.

Sample Selection: During the Post Liberalisation Period i.e., from 1991 to 31st March 2017, 22 Mergers have taken place in the Banking Sector in India between various Banks. Some of them were forced mergers (Private Sector Bank merged with Public Sector Bank) and a few were voluntary in nature. Indian oversees Banks took the first step to move on with merger for several reasons during the period of global financial crisis. Therefore, the study is undertaken to analyse the performance of the select Banks that have participated in the merger activity voluntarily.

Tools for Analysis: The tools for analysis used are Percentages and Averages

Purpose of Mergers and Acquisitions

The purpose of mergers and acquisitions will be reflected in corporate objectives. It needs to determine the specific goals to be achieved through acquisition. The basic purpose of a merger or business combination is to achieve rapid growth. Rapid growth can be achieved through product improvement and competitive positioning. Other possible purposes may be:

- Procurement of supplies
- Revamping production facilities
- Market expansion and strategy
- Financial strength
- General gains
- Own developmental plans
- Strategic purpose

Reasons for Bank Merger

- 1) Merger of Weaker Banks: The Narasimhan Committee opposed this method even though there is training to merge weak banks with strong banks in order to stabilize weak banks. Mergers can diversify risk management.
- 2) Increasing market competition: The innovation of new financial product and the consolidation of the local financial system are the reasons for the merger. Markets have expanded and become more competitive, as the market share of all individual firms has diminished and mergers and acquisitions have begun.
- 3) Scale Economy: The ability to create economies of scale when firms merge.
- 4) Skill and competence: Skill transfer takes place between two organizations, which helps to improve and become more competitive.
- 5) Technology, new services and products: Introduction to e-banking and some financial instruments / derivatives. Removing the barrier of entry has opened the gate for new high-tech banks, and old banks cannot compete with them, so they decide to merge.
- 6) Positive synergies: When two companies merge, their sole goal is to create a positive effect, which is higher than the combined effect of the two individual companies. Cost synergy and revenue synergy are two aspects of this.

Some other reasons

The sick banks escaped after the merger and improved branch network of the branch.

Omer Large customer base (rural range) and increased market share.

Infrastructure Achievement of infrastructure, restrict competition, curb banks, and utilize unutilized resources so that banks can compete with foreign banks in the global age.

The mergers and acquisitions have definitely shaped the Indian banking sector. Although there may be different opinions on this particular issue, there is always the expectation that the current situation will improve after the bank merger.

Merger of Bharat Overseas Bank with Indian Overseas Bank Bharat Overseas Bank

Merger of Bharat Overseas Bank with Indian Overseas Bank, Bharat Overseas Bank was originally designed to anchor the Indian operations abroad. In 1969, after the nationalization, the provocation demanded the closure of the banking branch by the Thai government. For four years the government blocked Thai pressure. Following the RBI initiative in 1973, six private sector

banks merged with IOB to form Bharat Overseas Bank. The Indian government has now reached an agreement with Thailand. The Reserve Bank allowed Krung Thai Bank Public Company to open its shop in India and the Thai gesture was ready to respond. Therefore, there is no problem in acquiring IOB bob. Bob had 30% of the IOB. Other partners in the bourse are Bank of Rajasthan (16%), Vysya Bank (14.66%), Federal Bank (10.67%), Karur Vysya Bank (10%), South Indian Bank (10%) and Karnataka Bank (8.67%). . In March 2005, Bob had an equity base of Rs.500. 15.75 crores. In addition, the total assets were Rs 198 crore. In 2007, Bob merged with IOB. The bank, which has a network of 103 branches, was acquired by IOB on April 3, 2007.

Merger of Kotak Mahindra bank and ING Vysya Bank

Kotak Mahindra Bank is an Indian private sector bank headquartered in Mumbai, India. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) was licensed by Kotak Mahindra Finance Limited, the group's flagship company, in February 2003. It offers a wide variety of banking products and financial services to corporate and retail customers through various delivery channels and affiliates in the areas of Personal Finance, Investment Banking, General Insurance, Life Insurance and Wealth Management. Kotak Mahindra Bank has a network of 1,369 branches spread across 689 locations and 2,363 ATMs. It is the second largest private bank in India by market capitalization after HDFC Bank in 2018.

ING Vysya Bank is a privately owned Indian multinational bank with retail, wholesale and private banking platforms formed since the Dutch ING Group acquired an equity stake in Vysya Bank in 2002. This merger marked the first time between an Indian bank and a foreign bank. Prior to the deal, Vysya Bank had a seven-year-old strategic alliance and shareholding arrangement with former Belgian bank Braxelles Lambert, which was acquired by ING Group in 1998.

In March 2013, ING Vysya was the seventh largest country in the private sector with a total assets of \$ 54,836 billion (US \$ 7.6 billion) and operates a pan-India network of over 1,000 lets outlets, including 527 branches, serving more than two million customers. On November 20, 2014, ING Vysya Bank decided to merge with Kotak Mahindra Bank, making it the fourth largest private bank in India. On April 1, 2015, the Reserve Bank of India approved the merger. On 15 May 2016 the merger process was completed.

Table No.2

Financial performance of Indian Overseas Bank and Kotak Mahindra bank for three years before merger

	Indian Overseas Bank			Kotak Mahindra bank		
	2004	2005	2006	2011	2012	2013
Number of Employees	24382	24366	24178	11638	12000	13500
Net worth Per Employee (Rs. Lakh)	232.51	269.48	354.78	101.01	114.39	118.28

Profit Per Employee (Rs. Lakh)	2.10	2.66	3.22	13.72	15.56	16.26
Net worth (Rs.Lakh)	5669058.52	6566149.68	8576661.94	1175611.59	1372730.04	1596849.15
Total Profit (Rs. Lakh)	51202.2	64813.56	77853.16	159722.52	186728.19	219562.85
Investment and Advances (Rs. Cr.)	40467	44220	53708	67290	84802	107165
Interest income (Rs.Cr.)	3754	3951	4406	5973	8470	10838
Other Income (Rs.Cr.)	741	800	541	5090	4543	5112
Return on Advances (%)	1.08	1.32	1.32	2.13	2.00	1.90
Net NPA Ratio (%)	2.85	1.27	0.65	1.13	0.5	0.6

Source: Researcher's compilation from financial statement of banks retrieved from annual reports of concerned financial years

Table no.3
Financial performance of Indian Overseas Bank and Kotak Mahindra bank for three years after merger

	Indian Overseas Bank			Kotak Mahindra bank		
	2008	2009	2010	2015	2016	2017
Number of Employees	24947	25512	26892	18335	31410	33013
Net worth Per Employee (Rs. Lakh)	582.7	689.5	712	125.87	109.80	120.67
Profit Per Employee (Rs. Lakh)	4.82	5.20	2.6	16.68	10.99	14.99
Net worth (Rs.Lakh)	14536616.9	17590524	19147104	2307850	3449097	3983796
Total Profit (Rs. Lakh)	120244.54	132662.4	69919.2	305832	345340	495111

Investment and Advances (Rs. Cr.)	88876.5	106100.7	116649.8	134221.1	215066.71	235586.44
Interest income (Rs.Cr.)	7738.8	9641.4	10245.8	13318.8	20401.6	22324.20
Other Income (Rs.Cr.)	1037.1	1598.8	1143.3	30588.32	3453.40	11659.59
Return on Advances (%)	1.30	1.17	0.53	2.06	1.42	1.79
Net NPA Ratio (%)	0.60	1.33	2.52	0.8	0.9	1.1

Source: Researcher's compilation from financial statement of banks retrieved from annual reports of concerned financial years

Table no.4

Average of different parameters of the two banks in the pre and post-merger period

Parameters	Period	Indian overseas bank		Kotak Mahindra bank	
		Mean	Change (%)	Mean	Change (%)
Business Per Employee (Rs. Lakh)	Pre	285.59	131.59	112.22	5.85
	Post	661.4		118.78	
Profit Per Employee (Rs. Lakh)	Pre	2.66	58.27	15.18	(6.32)
	Post	4.21		14.22	
Investment and Advances (Rs. Cr.)	Pre	46131.66	125.17	86419	125.59
	Post	103875.66		194958.08	
Interest income (Rs.Cr.)	Pre	4037	128.10	8427	120.49
	Post	9208.66		18581.33	
Other Income (Rs.Cr.)	Pre	694	81.52	4915	209.94
	Post	1259.73		15233.77	
Return on Advances	Pre	1.24	(19.35)	2.01	(12.93)

(%)	Post	1		1.75	
Net NPA Ratio (%)	Pre	1.59	(6.91)	0.74	25.67
	Post	1.48		0.93	

Source: calculated from values of table 2 & 3

Based on table 2, 3 & 4; After calculating the pre-merger and post-merger average values for different variables it was found that all of the variables have showed a positive as well as a negative change. Comparison of pre-merger and post-merger average of Business per employee has improved by 139.59% for IOB whereas 5.85% for Kotak Mahindra bank, profit per employee has improved in IOB but has declined for the other. Similarly, Investment and Advances have increased by 125% for both the banks. Interest Income of the both banks have also improved. Other income of the IOB has increased by 81.52% and for Kotak Mahindra bank by 209.94%. Return on Advances for both banks showed a decreasing trend and NPAs of IOB have decreased by 6.91% whereas for Kotak Mahindra it has increased.

Findings

The following are the findings of the study:

- During the period between 1991 – 31st march 2017 in total twenty-two mergers have taken place in Indian Banking Sector
- During the pre-merger period the number of employees in Kotak Mahindra was comparatively lesser
- All the key parameters in post-merger case of Kotak Mahindra Bank and IOB recorded increase in all except its return on advances
- During the post-merger period, the net worth and overall profitability of both the banks showed an increasing trend
- Investments and advances of both banks has tremendously increased

Conclusion

Merger in general is considered as a strategic tool for the participants in merger activity for gaining certain synergies. The study focused on the pre- and post-merger performance of IOB with Bharat overseas bank and Kotak Mahindra Bank with ING vysya bank, who have participated in mergers for different reasons. Overall growth is observed in the performance of both the banks in key parameters, and productivity ratios, and the same is ascertained by employing the statistical tools. But before allowing mergers to proceed, it must be ensured that certain conditions must be satisfied so that merger proves to be beneficial for all the concerned. Clear reasons must exist for M&A, which may include revenue growth, lower costs and improved return on assets. Merger should not only create strong domestic banks, but these banks should also be in the position to compete internationally. Market driven merger is most desirable.

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